

Design, Manufacturing and Optimization of Brake system in FSAE (EV) Vehicle

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Abstract— The study and design of a braking system for sports cars is the main emphasis of the current project. The braking system will be used in a car being created by the team Ethan racing electric to compete in the formula Bharat international collegiate design competition. The competition assesses the engineering, performance, and price of a Formula-style automobile. The values were evaluated and approximated for the under-design vehicle because it was the initial vehicle of this sort to be designed at team Ethan racing electric. To create a brake system that can satisfy the technical specifications of the competition, a technique has devised utilizing the theory of vehicle dynamics. Another aspect of this research was utilizing Finite Element Analysis (FEA), namely the ANSYS software version 2023, to analyses the behavior of brake rotors, brake mounts, pedals composed of various materials (Grey Cast Iron, Aluminum Alloy), and geometry (Drilled, Solid). For the design, static and thermal simulations were used. This leads to the demonstration of a braking system assembly that can achieve a four-wheel lock. In terms of thermal and static performance. Also, this year we are going to integration with electronics system which is BSPD (brake system plausibility device). This abstract's conclusion highlights the ongoing work being done on a braking system pause mechanism that will be incorporated into Formula SAE cars. This technology has the potential to transform the way FSAE cars are built and raced by adding an extra layer of safety and performance improvement. Additionally, it advances the larger subject of autonomous driving and vehicle safety technology.

Keywords— Formula Student, FEA, Vehicle Dynamics, Transient Thermal Analysis, Static Structural Analysis, BSPD And Electronic Vehicle

I. INTRODUCTION

The Formula SAE (FSAE) race car's braking system is an essential part that is crucial to the vehicle's performance and

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safety. This system's goal is to effectively slow down or stop the automobile by converting kinetic energy into thermal energy. In FSAE, the idea of braking is centred on control, efficiency, and accuracy. Braking produces severe forces and temperatures, therefore high-performance callipers, brake pads, and rotors are carefully chosen and built to manage them.

The hydraulic actuation of the system is precisely calibrated to offer the driver precise modulation, enabling the best possible cornering and deceleration. Additionally, obtaining optimal braking performance without creating instability depends on the balance between front and rear brake bias. The FSAE vehicles' braking mechanism is evidence of the complex engineering and design work required to create these open-wheel race cars that are both quick and secure. However, a number of serious issues with the external brake were discovered. while an example, the brake began to squeal while the automobile was climbing a slope and ultimately failed, causing the car to slide backward.

II. CALCULATIONS

A. Vehicle calculation:

It is important to note that all relationships assume optimal system performance. The following Table (2) list dimensions in normal international units.

1) Dynamic load on axels

We had to do a dynamic load calculation to determine the required torque on each axle in order to validate and certify the chosen components:

a) Dynamic load of the front axel

Figure 1 Schematic of Hydraulic Brake System

$$W_f = w \frac{l_2}{L} + w * \mu * \frac{h}{L}$$

Where:

W_f : Dynamic load on the front axle,

w: Weight of the vehicle,
L: Wheelbase,
l₂: length from the rear axle to CG,
μ: Coefficient of friction,
h: Centre of gravity.

$$W_f = 2943 \frac{0.912}{1.6} + 2943 * 0.7 * \frac{0.29}{1.6}$$

$$\underline{W_f = 2050.90 \text{ N}}$$

b) Rear axle

$$W_r = w \frac{l_1}{L} + w * \mu * \frac{h}{L}$$

$$W_r = 2943 \frac{0.688}{1.6} - 2943 * 0.7 * \frac{0.29}{1.6}$$

$$\underline{W_r = 892.09 \text{ N}}$$

2) Weight distribution percentage Front

$$Kbf = W_f / W$$

Where:

a) Front

Kbf: Front dynamic weight transfer.

$$Kbf = 2050.90/2943$$

$$Kbf = 0.69 = 69\%$$

b) Rear

$$Kbr = W_r / W$$

Kbr: Rear dynamic weight transfer.

$$Kbr = 892.09/2943$$

$$Kbr = 0.30 = 31\%$$

3) Braking force

According to Jones and Childers, the average coefficient of friction between asphalt and rubber for a dry road is 0.7, thus if we assume that the vehicle mass is 300 kg, we can use Equation to determine the total braking force.

$$Fb = \mu * W$$

Where: **Fb**: Total braking force.

$$Fb = 0.7 * 2943 \text{ } Fb = 2060.1 \text{ N}$$

a) Front braking force:

$$Fbf = Kbf * Fb$$

Where:

Fbf: Front braking force.

$$Fbf = 0.699 * 2050.1 \text{ F}$$

$$bf = 1435.63 \text{ N}$$

b) Rear braking force:

$$Fbr = Kbr * Fb$$

Where:

Fbr: Rear braking force

$$Fbr = 0.303 * 2050.1$$

$$Fbr = 624.46 \text{ N}$$

4) Deacceleration of Vehicle

The total deacceleration of the vehicle can be calculated according to the following

Equation:

$$d = \frac{\mu * (W_f + W_r)}{\left(\frac{W}{g}\right)} = \frac{Fbr}{M}$$

Where:

d: Deacceleration of vehicle,

g: Gravity,

M: Mass.

$$d = \frac{450}{300}$$

$$\underline{d = 1.5 \text{ g}}$$

The vehicle's frontal deacceleration may be calculated using Equation

$$df = \frac{\mu * (W_f + W_r)}{\left(\frac{W}{g}\right)} = \frac{Fbr}{M}$$

Where:

df=Deacceleration of the vehicle on the front axle.

$$\underline{df = 1435.6/300}$$

$$\underline{df = 0.9 \text{ g}}$$

Similarly, Equation will be used to compute the vehicle's rear deceleration:

$$dr = \mu * (W_f + W_r) / (W/g) = Fbr/M$$

Where:

dr : Deacceleration of the vehicle on the front axle.

$$dr = 624.46/300$$

$$\underline{dr = 0.6 \text{ g}}$$

5) Torque on wheels

a) Torque on the front wheels is given as Equation:

$$Tff = R * W * Fbf$$

Where:

Tf: Torque on front wheels,

Rw: Wheel radius.
Tf = 1435.6 * 0.2286
Tf = 328.17 Nm
Each wheel = 164.08 Nm

b) Torque on the rear wheels is given by Equation:

Tfr = **Rw** * **Fbr**
Where:
Tr : Torque on rear wheels.
Tr 0.2286 * 300
Tr = 142.75 Nm
Each wheel = 71.375 Nm

6) Characteristics of certain components

The characteristics of each component of the braking system will be covered in this section, starting with the pedal and progressing to the tire.

a) Pedal

The 5:1 pedal ratio, one of the suggested ratios for manual systems, was found to be the one that best fit the design and computation.

b) Master Cylinder

Table 1 Specification Of Master Cylinder

Material	Aluminium Alloy
Weight	0.31kg
Bore size	19.1mm
Full Stroke	25.4 mm

Fp: Force on the pedal.
Fmc = 300 * 5
Fmc = 1500

By dividing the force acting on the master cylinder by its area, the hydraulic pressure was then calculated using the equation below.

- Pressure on the master cylinder

Pmc = **Fmc**/**Amc**

Where:

Pmc: Pressure on the master cylinder,

Amc: Area on the master cylinder.

Therefore, using Equation below, it is necessary to first estimate the master cylinder's area.

Amc = $\pi * D^2 / 4$

Where:

Db: Bore diameter.

Amc = $(\pi * [(15.87)]^2) / 4$

Amc = 252.015 * $[(10)]^{-6}$ m²

Using the computed values

Pmc = 1500 / 252.015 * 10⁽⁻⁶⁾

Pmc = 7.73 * 10⁶ N / [mm]²

c) Calipers

FCalliper = **Pmc** * **ACalliper**

Table 2 Specification Of Caliper

External diameter	160 mm
Internal diameter	50 mm
Thickness	5 mm

Where:

FCalliper: Force on the caliper,

ACalliper: Area of the caliper.

Based on the piston diameter, the area of the piston was calculated using the equation below.

ACalliper = $\frac{\pi * D_{CP}^2}{4}$

Where:

Dcp: Diameter of calipers piston.

ACaliper = $\frac{\pi * (30.5)^2}{4}$ = 730.616 * 10⁻⁶ m²

Fcaliper = 7.73 * 10⁶ * 730.616 * 10⁻⁶

Fcalliper = 5647.73 N

The clamping force is then calculated by multiplying the force generated in a caliper by the number of pistons in Equation.

FClamping = **FCalliper** * **Number of pistons**

Where:

FClamping: The clamping force of the caliper.

FClamping = 5647.73 * 2

FClamping = 11295.46

d) Pads

FFriction = μ_{pad} * **FClamping**

Where:

FFriction: Friction force of the pads,

μ_{pad} : Pads coefficient of friction.

FFriction = 0.39 * 11295.46

FFriction = 4405.22N

Each pad = 2202.61N

e) Rotors

Table 3 specification of rotor

External diameter	180 mm
Internal diameter	60 mm
Thickness	5 mm

Rear Rotor

Table 4 Rear Rotor specification

Piston Diameter	30.5 mm
Number of pistons	2
Disc Thickness	5 mm
Weight	0.24 kg

III. ELECTRONICS INTEGRATION IN BRAKE SYSTEM

A. Bots (Brake Over Travel Switch)

A brake over travel switch is a safety device (pull push type switch) used in braking systems of various vehicles, particularly those designed for performance or competition.

1) Function:

Monitors the movement of the brake pedal.
Cuts off the engine or restricts fuel delivery in case of excessive brake pedal travel (beyond a designated limit).

Figure 2 Bots Schematic

B. BSPD (Brake System Plausibility Device)

A Brake System Plausibility Device (BSPD) is an electronic control unit (ECU) that monitors the integrity and functionality of a vehicle's braking system. It acts as a safety watchdog, ensuring consistency and plausibility between various brake system sensor signals.

1) Function:

Receives and analyzes data from multiple brake system sensors, including:

- Brake pedal position sensor
- Brake pressure sensors
- Compares sensor readings and ensures they are within expected ranges and logical relationships.

- Detects inconsistencies or implausible data that might indicate a braking system malfunction.

C. Benefits of BSPD:

- Enhances overall brake system safety by detecting potential malfunctions before they lead to complete brake failure.
- Provides early warnings to the driver, allowing them to seek repairs and prevent accidents.
- Improves the effectiveness of other braking system components like ABS and EBD by ensuring they operate with reliable sensor data.

Figure 3 Schematic of BSPD

Figure 4 Actual BSPD

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results of the Formula SAE (FSAE) brake system evaluation have yielded valuable insights into the performance and effectiveness of the braking components employed in our racing vehicle. The comprehensive testing and analysis conducted on the brake system have demonstrated its ability to provide efficient deceleration and precise control under various racing conditions. The system exhibited consistent and reliable stopping power, allowing the driver to confidently maneuver the vehicle during high-speed racing scenarios.

Furthermore, the data collected during testing provided crucial information for optimizing the brake balance and ensuring the safety and performance of the vehicle. These

results underscore the successful development and implementation of a robust FSAE brake system that meets the stringent demands of competitive racing while adhering to safety standards.

Figure 5 CAD model of pedal box

A. Ansys Analysis

Figure 6 Brake mounts with FOS 2.2

Figure 7 Rotor analysis with maximum temperature at 225C

Figure 8 Acceleration pedal mount with FOS of 5.2

Figure 9 Brake Pedal with FOS OF 2.3

Figure 10 Acceleration Pedal With Total Deformation Of 0.83

B. ACTUAL BRAKE SYSTEM

Figure 11 Side View

Figure 12 Top View

Figure 13 Unsprung Assembly

Figure 14 Rear Assembly

C. BRAKING DISTANCE TESTING

Figure 15 Braking distance with respect to speed

V. CONCLUSION

The established effort was devoted to studying braking mechanisms and how they affect driving behavior and vehicle safety. Its main goal was to create a brake system that could be utilized in a formula student racing car. This was accomplished using a variety of techniques based on the theory of automobile dynamics as well as a kinematic and active examination of the decelerating system. The braking system provide adequate overall performance, optimum performance, as countless of its constraints have been selected based on a set of ideals advised by various automobile bibliographies. Although the outcomes of theoretical calculations utilizing several approaches and computer studies were satisfactory, it is still important to keep improving the braking system and, therefore, the vehicle's overall performance.

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